

STUDY OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE Pro72Arg POLYMORPHISM OF THE TP53 GENE AND THE RISK OF DEVELOPING CHRONIC HEART FAILURE

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Abstract. *This study was conducted among inpatients at the clinical bases of Andijan State Medical Institute. A total of 208 individuals were involved in the research to achieve the study's objectives and tasks. Molecular genetic studies were carried out at the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Hematology under the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.*

In patients with chronic heart failure, the heterozygous Pro/Arg genotype of the TP53 gene Pro72Arg polymorphism was significantly more prevalent compared to the control group, confirming its role as a susceptibility marker. In other words, individuals with the heterozygous Pro/Arg genotype had a 2.2 times higher risk of developing CHF than those without this genotype (48.5% vs. 30.5%; $\chi^2=7.1$; $P=0.008$; $OR=2.2$; 95% $CI: 1.22-3.80$).

The statistical analysis of the study results was performed using the standard software package OpenEpi V.9.2.

Keywords: TP53, CHF, polymorphism, heterozygous, Pro/Arg genotype.

Introduction

Despite significant advances in medicine, cardiovascular diseases (CVD) remain the leading cause of mortality worldwide. For several decades, deaths from pathologies associated with disruptions in various morphological elements of the heart and its blood-supplying vessels have consistently ranked first globally [1,2].

One of the modern and promising approaches to preventing premature mortality in patients with coronary artery disease (CAD) and manifesting chronic heart failure (CHF) is the identification of risk factors for the development of ischemic left ventricular (LV) remodeling and myocardial apoptosis. [6]. These factors contribute to the unfavorable progression of the disease, leading to an increase in CHF severity by one or more functional classes (FC) according to the NYHA classification, repeated hospitalizations due to CHF, a decline in LV systolic function, recurrent myocardial infarctions (MI), the development of pulmonary embolism, and fatal outcomes within 12 months of follow-up [3,4]. One such approach includes molecular testing of genes referred to as "**susceptibility genes**" or **candidate genes** [5].

According to several researchers, hereditary variants (polymorphisms) of these genes are compatible with life but, when combined with unfavorable external factors (medications, diet, bad habits, infections, environmental pollution, etc.), can lead to various pathological conditions and diseases, including atherosclerosis, CAD, and CHF [7].

The identification of genetic markers may help optimize individualized therapy for each patient.

Research Materials and Methods

During the study, 103 patients from the main group were categorized into three subgroups based on the recommended clinical classification:

- Group 1: 33 patients with CHF VC-II diseases.
- Group 2: 37 patients with CHF VC-III diseases.
- Group 3: 33 patients with CHF VC-IV diseases.

The comparison group consisted of 105 conditionally healthy individuals.

Genomic DNA samples matching the patients in the study group by sex and age were used as control samples. These DNA samples were independently obtained from conditionally healthy individuals who, along with their close relatives, showed no clinical signs of the aforementioned diseases. The samples are stored in the DNA bank of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Hematology under the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The analysis of gene polymorphism association was performed using the "case-control" model (a case-control study comparing two samples).

Mutation testing was carried out on a Rotor-Gene Q (Quagen, Germany) device using a commercial test kit from "Sintol" LLC (Russia).

Statistical processing of the results was performed using the standard OpenEpi V.9.2 application software package.

Obtained results and their discussion.

The next stage of the genetic study aimed to determine the significance of the TP53 gene Pro72Arg polymorphism in the development of CHF.

We found the Pro allele in 31.0% of the main patient group and 19.0% of the control group ($\chi^2=8.0$; $P=0.005$; $OR=1.9$; 95% CI: 1.22-3.02). The mutant Pro allele of the TP53 gene Pro72Arg polymorphism contributed to the susceptibility to the development of this pathology (Table 1).

Conversely, the wild-type Arg allele was more prevalent in the control group than in the patient group, indicating its protective effect against disease development (69.0% vs. 81.0%; $\chi^2=8.0$; $P=0.005$; $OR=0.5$; 95% CI: 0.33-0.82) (Table 1).

Table 1

Comparative analysis of the distribution of TP53 gene Pro72Arg polymorphism alleles and genotypes in samples from the main and comparison groups.

Alleles and Genotypes	Number of Alleles and Genotypes Tested				χ^2	p	OR	95%CI
	Main Group n=103		Comparison group n=105					
	n	%	n	%				
Pro	64	31.0	40	19.0	8.0	0.005	1.9	1.22-3.02
Arg	142	69.0	170	81.0	8.0	0.005	0.5	0.33-0.82
Pro/Pro	7	6.8	4	3.8	0.9	0.3	1.8	0.52-6.49
Pro/Arg	50	48.5	32	30.5	7.1	0.008	2.2	1.22-3.80
Arg/Arg	46	44.7	69	65.7	9.3	0.002	0.4	0.24-0.74

Although the Pro allele of the TP53 gene Pro72Arg polymorphism reached statistical significance in the patient group compared to the control group, the distribution frequency values of the mutant Pro/Pro genotype did not reach statistically significant levels between the groups.

However, despite the insignificant differences, there is a weak tendency for an increased risk of SIOE when this genotype is present (6.8% vs. 3.8%; $\chi^2=0.9$; $P=0.3$; OR=1.8; 95% CI: 0.52-6.49) (Table 1).

The decrease in the frequency of the homozygous wild-type Arg/Arg genotype in the overall group of SIOE patients compared to the control group (44.7% vs. 65.7%) suggests its potential protective effect against the development of this pathology ($\chi^2=9.3$; $P=0.002$; OR=0.4; 95% CI: 0.24-0.74) (Table 1).

At the same time, a significant difference was found between the main patient group and the control group when analyzing the distribution of the heterozygous Pro/Arg genotype of the TP53 gene Pro72Arg polymorphism.

Notably, this genotype was significantly more prevalent in the patient group compared to the control group, indicating its role as a susceptibility marker. In other words, individuals with the heterozygous Pro/Arg genotype had a 2.2 times higher risk of developing SIOE than those without this genotype (48.5% vs. 30.5%; $\chi^2=7.1$; $P=0.008$; OR=2.2; 95% CI: 1.22-3.80) (Table 1).

CONCLUSION

Thus, in our study, the **heterozygous Pro/Arg genotype of the TP53 gene Pro72Arg polymorphism** was significantly more prevalent in the main group of patients compared to the group of conditionally healthy individuals, indicating its role as a susceptibility marker. The likelihood of CHF **development** was **2.2 times higher** in patients with this genotype compared to those without it.

REFERENCES

1. Heusch G. Myocardial ischemia: lack of coronary blood flow, myocardial oxygen supply-demand imbalance, or what? // *Am J Physiol Heart Circ Physiol*. 2019;316(6):H1439–H1446. Doi: 10.1152/ajpheart.00139.2019.
2. Dumont P, Leu JI, Della Pietra AC 3rd, George DL, Murphy M. The codon 72 polymorphic variants of p53 have markedly different apoptotic potential // *Nat Genet*. 2003; 33(3):357–365. Doi: 10.1038/ng1093.
3. Kolovou V, Tsipis A, Mihas C, Katsiki N, Vartela V, Koutelou M, Manolopoulou D, Leondiadis E, Iakovou I, Mavrogeni S, Kolovou G. Tumor Protein p53 (TP53) Gene and Left Main Coronary Artery Disease. *Angiology* // 2018;69(8):730–735. Doi: 10.1177/0003319718760075
4. Tsao C. W., Aday A. W., Almarzooq Z. I., Anderson C. A., Arora P., Avery C. L., American Heart Association Council on Epidemiology and Prevention Statistics Committee and Stroke Statistics Subcommittee. Heart disease and stroke statistics - 2023 update: a report from the American Heart Association // *Circulation*. 2023. V. 147. №8. P. e93-e621.
5. Fleg J. L., Forman D. E. Aging Changes in Cardiovascular Structure and Function // *Handbook of Cardiovascular Behavioral Medicine*. 2022. P. 127-162. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-85960-6_6

6. Свеклина Т.С., Шустов С.Б., Колюбаева С.Н., и др. Генетические маркеры хронической сердечной недостаточности с сохраненной фракцией выброса. Современные проблемы науки и образования. 2021;(3):111
7. Shirazi LF, Bissett J, Romeo F, Mehta JL. Role of inflammation in heart failure. *CurrAtherosclerRep.* 2017;19(6):27. DOI:10.1007/s11883-017-0660-3